

IMPORTANCE OF PEER TUTORING IN LEARNING OF ECONOMICS

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Abstract

Teachers have been using various methods to create interest in learning of Economics. At college level, students learn concepts on their own through Observation, Field Trips, Seminars and Workshops. Peer Tutoring is a new concept to teach Economics. Team Learning, Group Teaching and Co-operative Learning Strategies are Traditional methods used by the teachers in the classroom. We shall discuss about the importance of Peer Tutoring in learning of Economics.

Key words : Peer Tutoring

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Introduction :

In the present era, teachers use blended teaching strategies, mass media and multimedia to teach different subjects. Economics is an important subject which is helpful for the students in their professional lives. The Principles of Economics are complex and students have to understand them in order to deliver a good performance in their exams.

Peer Tutoring is one such technique which helps students make groups and learn the principles of Economics together. They can understand and comprehend in simpler ways.

Definitions of **Peer Tutoring** : It is a flexible strategy that involves peer interaction between tutors and tutees for academic purposes.

Peer tutoring is a teaching strategy that uses students as tutors. The student pairs might work on academic, social, behavioral, functional, or even social skills. There are many different ways to pair students, such as by ability level, skills mastered, or age. The following model descriptions will assist you in selecting the correct model based on certain criteria.

Implementation :

Peer tutoring includes a range of approaches in which learners work in pairs or small groups to provide explicit teaching support. There are two main types of peer tutoring: same age and cross age. In cross-age peer tutoring, an older learner takes the tutoring role and is paired with a younger tutee or tutees. There are also a number of same-age approaches such as Reciprocal Teaching, where learners alternate between the role of tutor and tutee, and Peer-Assisted Learning. The common characteristic of

all these approaches is that learners take on responsibility for aspects of teaching and for evaluating the success of their peer or peers.

In most peer tutoring approaches learners are instructed in how to undertake their roles effectively, often using specific and structured aspects of an interaction.

Importance and Benefits of Peer Tutoring :

Peer tutoring allows for higher rates of student response and feedback, which results in better academic achievement. It also creates more opportunities for students to practice specific skills, which leads to better retention. The student tutor gains a deeper understanding of a topic by teaching it to another student. Students involved in peer tutoring generally show a more positive attitude toward learning and develop self-confidence.

Peer tutoring often helps students build relationships and practice appropriate social interaction in the virtual classroom.

Benefits to Students Receiving Tutoring :

Studies have shown that participation in tutoring programs results in both academic and affective improvements for a variety of at-risk students including learning disabled, English language learners, low achieving students, students from underprivileged backgrounds and students with behavioral challenges. Students receiving tutoring improved academic performance, study skills, organization, classroom participation and motivation. Students also benefited from the opportunity to interact with peers and older student role-models in a positive and productive manner demonstrating improved social skills and time on task. These benefits have been witnessed among both regular and special education students across a variety of different subject areas and at all grade levels including elementary school, middle school, high school and college.

Benefits to Students Serving as Peer Tutors or Cross-Age Tutors :

Students serving as tutors or classroom student aides also benefited greatly from participation in peer tutoring or cross-age tutoring programs. Tutors strengthened and deepened understanding of the content they were tutoring, gained an increased sense of confidence and personal efficacy and developed responsibility and empathy. Research also found that student tutors demonstrated improved attendance and reduced tardiness and truancy. Serving as a peer tutor, cross-age tutor or student classroom aide also provided students with the opportunity to gain insight into the learning process and a better understanding of the field of teaching.

Benefits to Teachers, Schools and Academic Institutions

The availability of peer tutoring or cross-age tutoring was found to be beneficial to schools in that it provided an opportunity for students to receive individualized attention and support in an extremely cost-effective manner. Utilizing peer tutors and student aides during class provided teachers with increased opportunities to differentiate instruction, time to more effectively manage behaviors and address individual student issues, the option to provide more guidance during small group work, and an increased ability to accommodate the diverse set of needs demonstrated by their students. Utilizing peer

and cross-age tutors promoted a more cooperative classroom environment and led to improved student attitudes toward the subject matter. Peer and cross-age tutoring programs also provided another avenue by which students who may otherwise be hesitant to approach teachers or professors could access help. Many students reported that they felt more comfortable and were less intimidated approaching a peer tutor or cross-age tutor to ask questions, discuss class material, gain clarification and receive extra assistance.

Meets the individual instructions and specific needs of the online students :

Involves guided practice

Offers one-to-one assistance

Increases opportunities to respond to smaller groups

Raises student engagement

Encourages higher levels of thinking

Literature Review :

Most researches have emphasized that Peer Tutoring is helpful in making the students adapt to new style of Learning. It makes them self confident and peer to peer interaction yields positive results. Improved concentration and engagement in the classroom, good attention span and rapport building amongst the class.

Indian and Foreign researches have discussed about new teaching strategies to make the sessions more enjoyable and less monotonous. Blended Learning, Constructivism, Co-operative learning and Group learning are helpful in Problem Solving and Critical Thinking. Brainstorming is used by asking students to give examples and share personal experiences. Small Collaborative Group Learning also enhances the sessions. These Innovative Strategies can make the learning of Economics more Interesting, Enjoyable and Interactive.

As per the findings, Peer Tutoring was found to be more effective as compared to the Traditional methods of Teaching. Researchers felt that by using Peer interaction strategy, the teachers improve the scores in Economics subject.

Conclusion :

Peer Tutoring is definitely a good way of engaging the students and making them self reliant. The Teacher can act as a Facilitator and Guide. This strategy can build trust and confidence amongst the peers. It can be a powerful way of learning the complex concepts of Economics and also be an alternative to lot of issues relating to low attention span and concentration in the class. It can address the problems of the students and develop critical thinking in them.

Thus we can say that Peer Tutoring concept is New but it can really achieve the objectives of creating interest in learning Economics.

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